

ISic0067

I.Sicily inscription 0067

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tyndaris

Place of origin (modern)

Tindari

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Severo[---]

2. Pio · Fel(ici) · Aϩ[g]((usto))[---]

3. col(onia) · Aug(usta) · Tyn[t]((anorum))

4. numini · eius [devota]

Apparatus

Text of

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491856

EDR 142428

EDCS 22100595

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7476 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650805>)

Bivona, L. 1970. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelia*. Palermo. At 68

Fasolo, M. 2013. Tyndaris e il suo territorio. Volume 1. Introduzione alla carta archeologica del territorio di Tindari. Rome. At 75 no.9 fig.39

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